

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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THE EFFECT OF TELEHEALTH DIABETES SELF-MANAGEMENT EDUCATION AND
SUPPORT CLASSES ON DIABETIC GLYCEMIC CONTROL

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

The prevalence of diabetes mellitus type 2 has increased over the past decade and is associated with health complications and increased healthcare costs. Current evidence endorses diabetes self-management and education support (DSMES) classes to improve glycemic control. In addition, telehealth services improve patient access to healthcare while overcoming barriers such as geographical location, transportation, and exposure to communicable diseases. This DNP project aimed to improve glycemic management in adults with uncontrolled DMT2 by implementing interactive telehealth DSMES classes in the outpatient setting. The Plan-Do-Study-Act Model and the Lev Vygotsky Collaborative Learning Theory guided the intervention. A convenience sample of nine patients from a federally qualified health center in an urban community of Southern California consented to participate in this pilot program. A Mann-Whitney U Test analysis of pre-and post-serum glycated hemoglobin (HgbA1C) reflected improved aggregate HgbA1C for this project's sample. The daily blood glucose (BG) levels improved for the two participants who submitted logs. Despite only two participants completing daily BG logs, the daily BG levels improved over the five weeks post-DSMES implementation. Results of the Diabetes Knowledge Questionnaire reflected a higher degree of diabetes health literacy during DSMES classes, but post-intervention data did not reflect knowledge retention. A five-point Likert scale satisfaction survey reflected high satisfaction from the program's participants. With recommendations for adjusting future cycles, this project adds evidence that telehealth DSMES classes may offer improved diabetic glycemic control while minimizing patient barriers.

Keywords: diabetes, diabetes mellitus, self-management, DSMES, education, online, remote, telehealth, virtual

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Background

Diabetes mellitus is a complex disease that affects 37.3 million people, or 11.3%, of the United States (US) population (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2022c). Managing diabetes mellitus involves increased medical costs that are twice as high as individuals who do not have diabetes (CDC, 2022c). Annual expenditures for diabetes care in 2012 were estimated at \$245 billion; in 2022 it is an estimated \$327 billion (CDC, 2022c; Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services [CMS], 2019). In addition to increased costs, diabetes mellitus can cause serious complications such as, but not limited to, peripheral neuropathy, insufficient peripheral circulation, delayed healing from infections, diabetic nephropathy, and diabetic retinopathy (American Diabetes Association [ADA], 2022c; Chakraborty et al., 2020).

The literature shows that diabetes self-management education and support (DSMES) classes effectively improve glycemic control in those with diabetes mellitus (ADA, 2022c; Beck et al., 2017; Chrvala et al., 2016; Davis et al., 2022; Lynch et al., 2019; Wayne et al., 2015). DSMES classes include content on diabetes pathophysiology and treatment options; healthy eating; physical activity; medication usage; monitoring and using patient-generated health data (PGHD); preventing, detecting, and treating acute complications; preventing, detecting, and treating chronic complications; healthy coping with psychosocial issues and concerns; and problem-solving (Beck et al., 2017; Davis et al., 2022). The CDC created a DSMES toolkit as a comprehensive resource for those interested in implementing DSMES services (CDC, 2022b).

Problem Statement

Despite the evidence of DSMES efficacy, it is estimated that fewer than 7% of individuals with diabetes with private insurance, and less than 5% of individuals with diabetes who Medicare covers utilize DSMES interventions (Chrvala et al., 2016). Possible causes of underutilization are inadequate referrals for DSMES services, the limited number of DSMES providers, difficulty of patient accessibility, lack of administrative leadership support, lack of perceived benefit, and limited reimbursement rates (ADA, 2022c).

The recent COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the utilization of telehealth services. Through telehealth services, patients can access healthcare remotely. The shift of healthcare delivery from traditional in-person care to remote technology-enabled care has increased patient engagement. Emerging evidence demonstrates that this shift provides comparable and improved health outcomes (ADA, 2022c). In addition, the COVID-19 pandemic revealed that patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus faced higher mortality rates due to complications from acute infection, which can be contributed to the innately immunocompromised state associated with poor glycemic control (Chakraborty et al., 2020; Pal & Bhadada, 2020). The CMS define uncontrolled diabetes as a serum glycosylated hemoglobin (HgbA1C) greater than 9.0% (CMS, 2019). Given the continued progression of technology-enhanced medical care, delivery of DSMES classes through remote telehealth services has the potential for favorable diabetes management without the inconveniences of in-person visits (Chrvala et al., 2016; Orlando et al., 2019).

This DNP project took place at an outpatient federally qualified health center (FQHC) in Southern California. As of January 1, 2022, the project site had 1247 patients ages 18 to 74 with a diagnosis of Diabetes Mellitus of either Type 1 or Type 2. Two-hundred ninety-three of those patients, or 23%, were considered as having uncontrolled diabetes. The project site had no diabetes-specific educational program at the clinic to support these patients with self-managing diabetes mellitus. Therefore, the focus of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) quality improvement (QI) project was to implement synchronous remote group telehealth DSMES

educational sessions incorporating the CDC DSMES toolkit at the FQHC clinic. The goal was to improve glycemic control in patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, mitigating the development of serious complications from the disease.

Purpose Statement

The aim of this DNP project was to implement interactive telehealth DSMES classes and evaluate its effect on glycemic control amongst adults with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus type 2 (DMT2) in the outpatient setting.

Theoretical Framework

Two frameworks guided this DNP project. Lev Vygotsky's Collaborative Learning Theory (CLT) provided theoretical structure and support for synchronous telehealth educational sessions in this DNP project. The DNP project applied the Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) Model of Improvement to guide the application of QI practice change. This section describes both frameworks in detail.

Collaborative Learning Theory

Lev Vygotsky, a Russian psychologist who developed his theory of cognitive development simultaneously with Piaget, authored the CLT (McLeod, 2018; Miller, 2013). He died at the age of 38, before developing the comprehensive realization of his theory. Nonetheless, academics have reproduced Vygotsky's theory and have credited his work as a foundation for research on cognitive development (McLeod, 2018; Miller, 2013.). Lev Vygotsky did not title his theory; however, it has been popularly described as the Sociocultural Learning Theory and the CLT. This academic paper will refer to it as the CLT.

Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory and Vygotsky's CLT contain parallels and contrast as Vygotsky's original writings often referenced Piaget and critiqued Piaget's early theory descriptions. It is worth mentioning because both theories complement each other in understanding the development of cognition through childhood. Its application to adult learners is described later in this section. While Piaget described cognitive development as a spontaneous transition through stages, Lev Vygotsky emphasized that cognitive development relied heavily on cultural and social influence (McLeod, 2018; Miller, 2013.). He described words as signs that cultures attached to concrete items. Vygotsky distinguished between spontaneous concepts and scientific concepts. He defined spontaneous concepts as innate understandings of the world without the need for direct or deliberate instruction, and scientific concepts as abstract thinking that is developed through socialization. The development of cognition became possible through the integration of outward speech and inward speech as children learned words and refined language. Vygotsky described outward speech as the formation of words directed for the communication of thoughts, and inward speech as the process that allowed for internal processing and development of scientific concepts.

In CLT, learning is promoted through shared problem-solving between students and teachers and between students and other students. Vygotsky described three levels of learning: concepts that the learner can achieve on their own, concepts the learner can achieve with some help, and concepts they cannot achieve even with help. The CLT emphasizes the level at which the learner can achieve understanding of new scientific concepts with the help of others. Vygotsky described this area as the Zone of Proximal Development. Using outward speech in socialization and collaborative problem-solving, learners can process the information through internal speech to form new scientific concepts. With internalization of the shared knowledge, this information moves into the level of knowledge the learners can then achieve on their own, a process Vygotsky described as scaffolding. Educators facilitate the social environment through

scaffolding to help complete a learning task. Considering the elements of shared problem-solving in active learning, Vygotsky's CLT is useful in the classroom setting, where learners can collaborate with peers and instructors to gain competency in a subject matter. Figure 1 in Appendix A depicts the levels of learning capabilities and their relationship to each other.

Collaborative Learning Theory in Adult Learners. Although originally developed to describe cognitive development in children, CLT application in adult learners reflects similar findings. A small mixed-methods study of 42 participants by Aschbrenner et al. (2016) evaluated the perceptions and experiences of a group-learning weight loss program using peer-to-peer support for adults ages 21 and older with serious mental illness and obesity. Participants were 56% female, with a mean age of 48.6 years. The researchers designed a program to empower the participants to make decisions in adjusting their lifestyle behaviors through shared problem-solving among their peers and guidance from lifestyle coaches. The participants were also encouraged to use mobile technology and social media to facilitate a social network with their peers and become accountable to the group. Participants answered two surveys and underwent a focus group interview. The results reflected an overall satisfaction with the hands-on learning and the group problem-solving activities. The common theme of "being in the same boat" gave the participants a sense of encouragement from experiencing the program with others they felt understood their health conditions (Aschbrenner et al., 2106). Although the participants expressed initial anxiety with working in small groups, the end perceptions were that they felt supported and could make new friends with similar experiences. The study resulted in 45% of participants achieving weight loss and 45% of participants improving fitness (Aschbrenner et al., 2016).

Ouyang et al. (2019) also performed a mixed methods analysis to examine how and to what extent the instructors and their students built a collaborative partnership in a graduate-level online course. Ouyang et al. (2019) found in their literature review that adult learners needed to be active in their own learning, incorporate their expertise, and respect the expertise of others. The collaborative partnership created an engaged learning community working together to achieve a shared goal (Ouyang et al., 2019). The researchers found that alternating between instructor-led and student-led discussions helped the instructor design the content summary based on the collective learning. The students shared that engaging in mutual interaction made them want to participate more because they felt their contributions added to the learning community. The researchers found that student and instructor participation frequency was nearly equal, indicating that students interacted socially with the online learning community. These findings support shifting from the instructor-directed method to the student-centered collaborative learning design (Ouyang et al., 2019).

Theoretical Concepts. CLT uses *spontaneous concepts* and *scientific concepts* to describe innate and learned knowledge, respectively. In this section describing the theoretical concepts of Vygotsky's CLT, the reader must distinguish between Vygotsky's definitions of concepts and conceptual elements within a theory. The theoretical concepts in Vygotsky's CLT include conscious awareness, imitation, instruction, and the zone of proximal development.

Conscious awareness requires introspection and logical thinking. It is when the learner acknowledges they are introduced to new words and ideas. This heightened attention sparks internal speech to connect the information with memory and perception.

Vygotsky describes the concept of imitation as mimicking the instructor's actions and language by the learner, helping to form new connections between words and thus developing new perceptions of understanding.

Instruction opens the gates to conscious awareness. Instruction introduces what Vygotsky referred to as scientific concepts or socialized connections of ideas. Instruction introduces a system of concepts that the learner would not be previously aware of if they were only exposed to ideas of concrete thinking. Vygotsky insisted that instruction must move ahead of development to be effective.

The zone of proximal development is the space where instruction, conscious awareness, and imitation simultaneously occur to bridge new ideas into the memory and perception of the learner. The interactive socialization in this space allows for integrating new knowledge into internalized understanding through collaborative problem solving, assisting the learner in performing at higher levels than they would on their own.

Assumptions. CLT contains three assumptions. The first assumption is that scientific concepts manifest from the learner's spontaneous concepts. That is, the learner must have some understanding of the world that is saturated by their own experience. The second assumption of the CLT is that scientific or socially learned concepts and spontaneous concepts have a fluid relationship. The development of scientific concepts depends upon the maturity of spontaneous concepts. Simultaneously, the emergence of scientific concepts influences a heightened understanding of spontaneous concepts. The third assumption under CLT is that learning from instruction involves internal and external processes. Teaching, the external factor, is the socialization of abstract thinking from a more knowledgeable person to the learner. Vygotsky expressed that the culture one is born into decides what concepts are introduced to the learner. The learner then forms connections and develops meaning from the information, constituting the internal learning process.

Application. This DNP project incorporated the theoretical concepts of conscious awareness, instruction, imitation, and the zone of proximal development from Lev Vygotsky's CLT through the application of synchronous telehealth group DSMES educational sessions. The telehealth DSMES sessions facilitated the culture of shared learning integral to the zone of proximal development. Participants gathered at designated times for virtual group meetings and were presented with educational information covering the topics of the DSMES curriculum. The concept of conscious awareness occurred as the participants logged into the virtual meeting room for the time allotted to focus on DSMES material. Instruction occurred when the educators provided information to meet the curriculum's objectives. The sessions provided sample scenarios for managing diabetes mellitus where participants had an opportunity to problem-solve. The sessions also incorporated sample solutions to the scenarios. The participants were provided additional scenarios and encouraged to interact and collaborate to develop solutions. The concept of imitation took place during this activity as the participants recalled and recreated solutions learned from the instructional portion of the session. The participants shared their responses with the whole group. Afterward, the educator synthesized, elaborated, and challenged the responses to facilitate understanding. The connection of newer thought processes from previous knowledge by participants supported Vygotsky's act of scaffolding in the zone of proximal development (Miller, 2013). A diagram of how telehealth DSMES fits with CLT is provided (Figure 2 in Appendix A).

The Model for Improvement

The IHI Model for Improvement (MI) (2022) served as the framework to apply and evaluate the QI practice change of this DNP project. MI attempts to answer three fundamental

questions: (1) What is the desired outcome? (2) How can a change be determined as an improvement? (3) What changes to the status quo will result in an improvement? (IHI, 2022; Langley et al., 2009). The IHI acknowledged that change is inevitable and that one can either let change happen to them or become proactive in making the change improve the product or practice outcomes. Because not all change is an improvement, MI applies an iterative cycle called the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) Cycle, which allows for rapid testing of change to determine if the change resulted in an improvement. This model suits well for QI endeavors as it maintains a pragmatic approach to test shifts in the system while monitoring for disturbances in the current process. The mechanics of testing and monitoring are discussed in the following section.

Concepts. IHI conveniently named the PDSA cycle with the elements of MI: plan, do, study, and act. Each test for change follows these steps in this order. Figure 3 in Appendix A displays MI in a concept map. Figure 4 in Appendix A shows the elements and details of the PDSA cycle.

Plan. The planning portion begins with the aim, often interchangeable with the purpose statement. This DNP project aimed to implement interactive telehealth DSMES classes to improve glycemic control amongst adults with uncontrolled DMT2 in the outpatient setting. Because this was a QI project and not a research study, there was no control group. The aggregate post-intervention HgbA1C and Diabetes Knowledge Questionnaire (DKQ) results were compared against the baseline, or pre-intervention, values. The project aim is relevant in diabetes management as improved glycemic control will delay or prevent serious complications of DMT2 (ADA, 2022c; Chakraborty et al., 2020; Pal & Bhadada, 2020).

During the planning stage, the QI team determined the process, outcome, and balancing measures. Process measures are the measurable data used to track the effect of the practice change. For this project, the process measure was self-generated blood glucose monitoring. This project contained two outcome measures: glycemic control, as evidenced by the HgbA1C, and health literacy, as evidenced by the DKQ results. The balancing measure was the element to observe to prevent the test of change from disrupting the current system. In this project, the number of hypoglycemic episodes experienced by participants weekly was the balancing measure. The QI project can inadvertently cause a heightened focus on lowering blood glucose that hypoglycemic events may occur. If this occurred, it might be possible that the intervention undesirably caused adverse effects.

The operational definitions for the family of measures were as follows. One educator (the project lead), one Spanish translator, and one classroom moderator facilitated the DSMES classes. A count of participant presence at the virtual DSMES meetings, logged by the designated DSMES classroom moderator, tracked attendance to the DSMES classes. The participants were instructed to obtain daily self-measurements of their fasting and non-fasting fingerstick blood glucose (BG) throughout the DSMES program. The ADA (2022a) defines fasting BG as a BG reading taken after at least eight hours of no food or beverages except water. Nonfasting BG is a reading anytime outside of the fasting window. The participants kept a log of their BG levels and emailed or texted the log weekly to the project lead. The DKQ, a validated tool that can be administered in English and Spanish to assess diabetes knowledge, was administered by the DSMES team at two points of the program, immediately before the first class session and immediately after the fifth and final class session (Garcia et al., 2001). The lead author extracted the HgbA1C values from the electronic health record (EHR) before the DSMES sessions and those reassessed six weeks after the first class session. The values were entered into

a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. The lead author, a licensed nurse practitioner, ordered the laboratory tests, which the affiliated laboratory processed. There were no associated costs for administering DKQ. There were no additional laboratory costs outside of standard costs from routine primary care visits. The project lead monitored the weekly BG logs for readings less than or equal to 70 mg/dL to ascertain that the DSMES educational sessions did not inadvertently cause hypoglycemic events (ADA, 2022c). Following the thorough planning of the QI project, the QI team proceeded to the Do segment of the PDSA cycle.

Do. The QI team implemented the interventions and collected the data generated during the planning stage of the PDSA cycle. During this stage, the QI team carried out the proposed change in practice and organized the data in Microsoft Excel. This DNP project implemented the telehealth DSMES sessions for the desired population and collected the data that coincided with the project's family of measures.

Study. During the study portion of the PDSA cycle, the QI team organized the data with diagrams, such as control charts and bar graphs. It used statistical analysis calculations available in Intellectus Software to observe any shifts in the post-intervention data compared to the data before implementing the practice change. The QI team evaluated whether the interventions affected the outcome measure as planned and whether the balancing measure demonstrated an undesirable effect on the current system. Analysis of the data determined if the change implemented brought an improvement to the system. Figure 5 in Appendix A shows the elements of the PDSA cycle adjusted for the details of this DNP project.

Act. After data analysis, the QI team decided on the following action: to either adopt the change, adapt the change, or abandon the change. Adopting the change occurs when the QI team determines that the intervention reflects an improvement to the current system. The QI team desires to scale up the intervention and implement the new practice change organization-wide. The QI team should adapt the change if the data show some improvement, but not to the desired degree. Lastly, the QI team may abandon the change if they conclude that the data reflect no improvement or an untoward effect on the balancing measure. For example, the team could consider abandoning the change if the balancing measure shows that the intervention is causing an undesirable effect on another aspect of the system. In this case, the QI team may opt to try an entirely different angle of approach.

Assumptions

The assumptions under MI are that not all change is an improvement, improvement can be achieved through rapid cycle tests, and cooperation of humans is needed to achieve improvement (IHI, 2022; Langley et al., 2009). MI states that change is inevitable and will occur whether stakeholders are actively causing the change or passively letting the change occur. Therefore, not all change will result in an improved system, and stakeholders must become involved in the change process to lead toward desirable outcomes. Furthermore, MI believes in rapid cycles of testing, an iterative process of performing small tests of change using the PDSA cycle, and continuously analyzing the data to make decisions for the next round of testing. Rapid cycles allow the QI team to make real-time pragmatic decisions to achieve the desired outcome. QI teams must repeatedly and continuously observe the data collected during the tests of change and analyze any trends. If the observed data are not reflecting the desired outcomes, the QI team must evaluate which areas of the process to continue, adjust, or reject. Rather than large-scale changes, the MI process works with small incremental tests of change and only recommends scaling up when the data reflect sustained improvements. Lastly, human cooperation is needed to create changes that result in systematic improvements. Creating and testing hypotheses do not

affect systems if resistance to practice change exists. The QI team must recruit the cooperation of members that will implement the changes to shift the status quo. Clear cyclical communication of the change purpose, process, and outcomes will aid participant motivation and involvement. Cyclical communication assisted the QI team in addressing the concerns and obstacles at the front-line level, giving opportunity to create change cycles that addressed these issues.

Review of Literature

A literature review to analyze the current evidence related to DSMES was conducted on the databases CINAHL, PubMed, APA PsychINFO, Scopus, OneSearch, and Google Scholar. The search terms included combination variations of “diabetes,” “diabetes mellitus,” “diabetes self-management education,” “DSME,” “virtual,” “online,” “digital,” “remote,” “technology,” “COVID-19,” “health behavior,” “health knowledge,” “education,” “collaborative learning,” “adult learner,” “outpatient,” “community clinic,” “reading level,” and “readability.” In addition, the author incorporated a search with the terms “telehealth,” “older adult,” “elderly,” and “geriatrics” to assess for special considerations in the older adult population. Inclusion criteria consisted of peer-reviewed articles, in English, and published from 2015 to 2022. Exclusion criteria included language other than English, the pediatric population, and acute care settings. The review of literature revealed four themes within the topic of DSMES: the prevalence of uncontrolled DMT2, health literacy, utilization of technology, and efficacy of DSMES.

Uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus Type 2

The CMS define uncontrolled DMT2 as a serum HgbA1C level greater than 9.0% (CMS, 2019). Uncontrolled DMT2 has an increased risk of end-organ damage such as, but not limited to, peripheral neuropathy, diabetic nephropathy, diabetic retinopathy, heart disease, and stroke. Complications such as impaired circulation and delayed wound healing can also lead to limb amputations (ADA, 2022c; CDC, 2022c; Chakraborty et al., 2020). Furthermore, a patient with DMT2 can expect an average annual medical expenditure of \$16,752, of which \$9,601 is spent solely on diabetes. Medical costs for a person with DMT2 are 2.3 times higher than those without diabetes (ADA, 2020). Improving HgbA1C decreases the risk of serious complications related to DMT2 and decreases all-cause costs. A 1% decrease in HgbA1C can result in a 45% less risk of developing chronic complications due to diabetes (Nathan, 2014). Additionally, a 1% decrease in HgbA1C can result in cost savings of 2% in all-cause medical costs and 13% in diabetes-related costs (Lage & Boye, 2020).

The Association Between COVID-19 and Diabetes Mellitus

An association between uncontrolled DMT2 and complications with COVID-19 infection has been described in the literature (Chakraborty et al., 2020; Pal & Bhadada, 2020). Chakraborty et al. (2020) found in their review of descriptive literature that the percentage of COVID-19 mortalities with co-existing diabetes ranged from 7.3% to 58%. People with diabetes are innately immunocompromised and are in a pro-inflammatory state. Combined with a COVID-19 infection, this can cause a cytokine storm and hypercoagulability, resulting in rapid deterioration. Treatment of COVID-19 with corticosteroids can lead to glycemic excursions, complicating the treatment of and recovery from COVID-19 for people with diabetes (Pal & Bhadada, 2020). Thus, the COVID-19 pandemic added an additional layer to the imperativeness of promoting glycemic control in persons with DMT2 while mitigating the risk of contracting communicable diseases.

Health Literacy

Health literacy is the acquisition and comprehension of health information, which can be used for disease management (Hoedebecke et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2018). Patient education material (PEM) helps promote health literacy as it gives the patient written documents to review after medical visits as well as to prepare for a future visit with their healthcare providers (Hoedebecke et al., 2017; Hutchinson et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2022; Lipari et al., 2019; Singh et al., 2018). PEM may contain information regarding disease pathophysiology, treatment options, nutritional interventions, lifestyle modifications, and medication instructions. A cross-sectional

study by Singh et al. (2018) found that 63% of the 263 participants had low health literacy scores, directly associated with greater difficulty understanding the written material for prescription instructions. Furthermore, analysis of the online PEM distributed by national organizations such as Mayo Clinic, WebMD, National Institute of Health (NIH), and Wikipedia found the PEM to be at reading levels of grades 10 to 14 (Hoedebecke et al., 2017; Hutchinson et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2022; Lipari et al., 2019). This is well above the recommended reading grade levels 6 to 8 proposed by the American Medical Association, NIH, and CDC (Hoedebecke et al., 2017; Hutchinson et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2022; Lipari et al., 2019). A sixth-grade reading level was the average reading level for the North American adult, revealing a gap in the availability of easy-to-understand health information (Singh et al., 2018).

Furthermore, health management education tailored to address and incorporate cultural norms and values helps improve health literacy (Benavides-Vaello & Brown, 2016; Rotberg et al., 2016). Culturally appropriate DSMES positively affected perceived social support, glycemic control, and preventative measures (Rotberg et al., 2016). Incorporating cultural values can help increase motivation for self-management and maintain a sense of self when balancing daily life with disease management and health promotion (Benavides-Vaello & Brown, 2016).

A validated and reliable tool to assess diabetes health literacy is the DKQ (Garcia et al., 2001). The DKQ is a 24-item questionnaire with corresponding answers of “yes,” “no,” or “I don’t know.” One point is given for each correct answer. The questionnaire was validated for use in both the English and Spanish languages. Results from the DKQ can guide education objectives and material to increase health literacy.

Technology in Health Education

Technological advances in healthcare propel ease of access to health information and education as well as facilitate ease of access to healthcare services remotely (Beck et al., 2017; Davis et al., 2022; Hoedebecke et al., 2017; Lipari et al., 2019; Orlando et al., 2019; Wayne et al., 2015). Telehealth is an alternative mode of healthcare service delivery using any combination of digital media, videoconferencing, telephone calls, and electronic messaging (Orlando et al., 2019). The recent COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the use of telehealth services, increasing patient engagement and yielding comparable results to traditional in-person visits (ADA, 2022c). Accessibility to healthcare providers from the comfort of one’s home mitigates geographical barriers, especially for those living in rural or remote areas, those with disabilities, or those who do not have easy access to transportation. Telehealth also mitigates absenteeism from work or family. Patients and their caregivers have reported satisfaction with telehealth services (Orlando et al., 2019).

Increased engagement through telehealth services and sharing of online PEM have helped achieve faster glycemic control in DMT2 (Lipari et al., 2019; Wayne et al., 2015). Some providers and health clinics have also engaged through social media to link patients with PEM (Hoedebecke et al., 2017). The 2022 update of the ADA Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes added support for telehealth services as an acceptable and efficacious mode for diabetes management (ADA, 2022c).

Challenges for Older Adults

Older adults face greater challenges to telehealth use that can be attributed to vision or hearing impairment, unfamiliarity with the technology and internet use, or not having access to a technological device (Choi et al., 2022; Wong et al., 2022). However, ownership of a computer

or tablet and receiving support to learn their operation have shown statistically significant increases in participation with telehealth services among adults aged 65 and older (Choi et al., 2022). Smartphone devices have not shown similar effects, likely due to their smaller screens that challenge visual reading and finger dexterity (Choi et al., 2022). Older adults who receive support to obtain familiarity with larger electronic devices exhibit an increased interest in seeking online health-promoting information and become more involved in active decision-making with their care plans. Furthermore, Jung et al. (2022) demonstrated that technology familiarity decreased computer anxiety, increased computer confidence, and provided an increased sense of self-efficacy. A systematic review of randomized controlled trials and meta-analysis performed by Wong et al. (2022) revealed improved quality of life among community-dwelling older adults who participated in nurse-led telehealth programs to support health-promoting behaviors. Thus, the literature shows a positive relationship between instructing older adults on using electronic devices, their use of telehealth services, and the quality of their lives in the community.

Efficacy of DSMES

DSMES assists patients in increasing DMT2 health literacy resulting in greater independence with self-management. There are four critical points to connect patients with DSMES: at initial diagnosis, annually, when complicating factors arise, and during transitions in care (Beck et al., 2017; Davis et al., 2022). Complicating factors include changes in health status, development of end-organ damage, need for steroid therapy, a complicated medication plan, family planning, pregnancy, physical or cognitive impairment, changes in mental health, and changes to socioeconomic factors such as sheltering, income, and food insecurities (ADA, 2022c). End organ damage includes irreparable deterioration of the renal, cardiovascular, nervous, or ophthalmic systems. The elements of DSMES include diabetes pathophysiology, nutrition, physical activity, medications, self-monitoring of glucose, acute and chronic complications, healthy coping, and problem-solving (Beck et al., 2017; Davis et al., 2022).

Compared to patients with DMT2 who have not received DSMES, participation with DSMES has shown a reduction of HgbA1C by 0.6% to 0.74% without side effects (Beck et al., 2017; Chrvala et al., 2016; Davis et al., 2022). Significant improvements in HgbA1C are achieved with DSMES contact time of greater than 10 hours, and sustained improvement in HgbA1C is achieved when the duration of DSMES is greater than 2.5 months (Beck et al., 2017; Chrvala et al., 2016; Davis et al., 2022; Lynch et al., 2019). Twelve months of engagement with DSMES has shown statistically significant improvements in health literacy regarding knowledge of nutrition and diet quality (Lynch et al., 2019). In addition, DSMES administered in a group setting where patients with DMT2 can engage in collaborative learning with other patients with DMT2 has shown improved glycemic control (Chrvala et al., 2016; Ory et al., 2020).

Collaborative Learning Theory in Chronic Disease

A qualitative study by Gucciardi et al. (2021) revealed the group process themes of knowledge exchange, collaborative learning, and reflection in peer-to-peer storytelling of diabetes management behaviors. The participants found peer-to-peer learning valuable, less intimidating, and more meaningful than the traditional patient-provider exchange. Peer learning encourages empowerment, engagement, and a supportive community (Gucciardi et al., 2021). The combined knowledge of DSMES efficacy and the positive feedback of a peer-to-peer learning environment supports the application of Lev Vygotsky's CLT with DSMES sessions.

Methods

Design

This was a QI project to implement interactive telehealth DSMES classes to improve glycemic control amongst adults with uncontrolled DMT2 in the outpatient setting. The CMS defines uncontrolled diabetes as an HgbA1C level greater than 9.0% (CMS, 2019). The DSMES Toolkit available on the CDC website (2022b) and outlined by the 2022 National Standards for Diabetes Self-Management and Support by Davis et al. (2022) guided the development of this DSMES program.

The application and evaluation of the program were guided by the PDSA cycle within the IHI MI framework (2022). The virtual classroom replaced the physical classroom in which participants would traditionally attend a group learning session. The total duration for data collection of the DNP project was six months, with a timeline from August 2022 to February 2023. The DSMES program was implemented in five weekly sessions of two simultaneous cohorts to accommodate daytime and late afternoon classes. The lead author designed the online version of the DKQ to be administered at weeks one, six, and 24 to evaluate the effect of DSMES classes on the participants' diabetes health literacy.

Setting

The project took place at an outpatient FQHC primary care clinic. The FQHC serves primarily low-income individuals and families of all ages. The FQHC system provides comprehensive primary and preventative care to all persons regardless of their ability to pay or health insurance status. The FQHC consumers are primarily covered by Medicaid or Medicare. Private insurance is also accepted. Programs for uninsured individuals are available to assure access to healthcare for anyone seeking care at the facility. The FQHC system is designed as a source for outpatient healthcare to reach the underserved population, including, but not limited to, migrant workers, people experiencing homelessness, and the undocumented.

The FQHC, where this DNP project implemented the DSMES program, has 12 locations within an urban setting. This project took place at one of the 12 sites, which reported 1,247 patients ages 18 to 74 with diabetes who sought care at the clinic between January 1, 2021, and December 31, 2021. Of these patients, 293, or 23.5%, had a HgbA1C reading greater than 9.0%.

Participants/Sample

The lead author identified eligible participants through a query of the EHR system for individuals with a HgbA1C of 9.0% or greater. The eligible participants were invited to participate in the telehealth DSMES program upon meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The author enrolled as many eligible participants as willing to participate, with a target of at least 30 participants. Starting with at least 30 participants would allow for attrition of up to 33% and maintain at least 20 participants from whom to collect, follow, and analyze data through the course of the first cycle of the project. Inclusion criteria required that a participant had the following: a diagnosis of diabetes mellitus type 2; a pre-participation HgbA1C greater than or equal to 9.0%; was aged 18 to 74; had access to an electronic device with video and sound capabilities; had a reliable internet or data plan; was receiving primary care from the project site; and spoke either English or Spanish. All genders were welcome to participate. Exclusion criteria consisted of participants diagnosed with diabetes mellitus type 1, prediabetes, hemodialysis status, or gestational diabetes. Diabetes mellitus type 1 (DMT1) differs from DMT2 in that in DMT1, the pancreas produces little to no insulin and is often diagnosed during childhood and adolescence. Individuals with DMT1 are insulin-dependent, whereas individuals with DMT2 may achieve glycemic control through lifestyle changes and without the use of insulin (CDC,

2022a). This DNP project focused on individuals with DMT2 because the initial onset more often occurs during adulthood. Among the multifactorial causes of DMT2, lifestyle behaviors serve a significant role in its development and management (CDC, 2022a). Prediabetes was excluded because this project focused on those who experienced inadequate glycemic control and were diagnosed with DMT2. End-stage renal disease with hemodialysis affects the accuracy of HgbA1C readings, often due to the associated chronic anemia and the decreased blood glucose and hemoglobin reaction time that collectively produce unreliable HgbA1C readings (Coelho, 2015). Gestational diabetes was an exclusion criterion because insulin resistance occurs secondary to hormonal changes during pregnancy, and management may be transient to the gestational period (CDC, 2022a). Participants who changed assignment of their primary care provider to a clinic other than the project setting were no longer eligible for the final data collection and analysis as the project lead no longer had access to their new electronic health record. Participants with intellectual or developmental delays were excluded due to limitations in independently managing their healthcare.

A review of the project setting patient demographics revealed that within the subgroup of patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, 241(82.25%) were Hispanic or Latino. Therefore, the DSMES sessions were provided simultaneously with audio options for both English and Spanish, and participants who did not speak English or Spanish were excluded from the project.

All participants were offered an initial instructional session for technology support through the Zoom virtual meetings platform before the DSMES program to ensure competency in navigating telehealth and the Qualtrics online survey platform via their electronic devices. Support was available throughout the program to assist participants with troubleshooting any technology issues they encountered.

Ethical Considerations

An IRB review and determination as non-research was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach, to ensure the protection of the human subjects. The project lead obtained a letter of approval from the project site's Chief Medical Officer (CMO) and Chief Executive Officer (CEO). After being identified as meeting inclusion criteria, the participants received information about the project through an invitational telephone call made by the Health Education and Outreach (HEO) department or through direct invitation from the project lead when an eligible participant was identified during routine telehealth or in-clinic healthcare visit. The participants preferred and consented to cellular phone text messaging over e-mail communication; therefore, a text message that outlined the project's purpose, goals, and the dates and times for the telehealth DSMES sessions was sent to each participant's cellular phone. An electronically signed informed consent form was collected before attending the DSMES sessions. Participation was voluntarily, and the refusal to enroll as a participant did not affect the quality of health services. The program leader and facilitators protected the participants' identities to maintain compliance with the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). The participants possessed control over the amount of self-identifying information they shared in the virtual group classes. All participants were notified that the program facilitators did not have control of any information they might share outside of the program setting; therefore, they were asked to respect the privacy of the group learning space. The project lead and DSMES team maintained patient data in the secured, password-protected EHR and the password-protected cloud approved by the project site's information technology (IT) department.

Procedures

Implementation of the QI project followed the PDSA cycle format.

Plan

The project lead partnered with the organization's HEO department, which had already established weekly telehealth group education classes entitled Healthy Mind, Body, and Soul, incorporating general education on nutritious food sources, types of physical activities to integrate into a daily routine, and self-regulating deep breathing exercises for general well-being. The program was provided through the Zoom virtual meetings platform and offered simultaneously in English and Spanish. The attendees could self-select the audible language of preference. This DNP project enhanced the existing program by offering diabetes-specific education for patients who have uncontrolled DMT2. The goal was to promote self-management behaviors to achieve effective glycemic control. The project lead ensured recruitment of participants through both telephone contact and text messaging to outline the DSMES program goals, curriculum, and process for informed consent to participate.

Timeline and Roles. Upon receiving approval from the CSULB IRB, the DNP project lead author planned to recruit and train the DSMES team throughout June and July 2022. The DSMES team comprised the project lead, a Spanish translator, and a Zoom virtual meeting room moderator. The room moderator admitted participants into the Zoom meeting room, monitored the chat box for questions and comments from participants, and assisted participants with any technological issues.

The DSMES sessions were planned to run from August 2022 to September 2022, with a proposed additional cohort from September 2022 through October 2022. The project lead facilitated each one-hour session and translated by the Spanish translator. A feature on Zoom was used so that participants could choose which language (English or Spanish) they preferred for the audio output. Each session began with five minutes of greeting and introduction to the session's learning objectives. The DSMES team then presented a PowerPoint slide show presentation for the remaining 55 minutes that integrated information sharing from the project lead and problem-solving prompts to stimulate collaborative discussion of the learning objectives. The amount of time spent on each subtopic within each session was driven by the questions and comments from the participants, allowing more time to be focused on concepts that the participants had greater difficulty understanding. The collaborative efforts for problem-solving incorporated scaffolding of new information in the Zone of Proximal Development under the CLT by Lev Vygotsky (McLeod, 2018; Miller, 2013). During the final five minutes of each session, the lead author summarized the main themes and take-home messages, then briefly introduced the topic of the following session. The participants were asked to complete a brief 3-question 5-point Likert scale satisfaction survey in Appendix B via Qualtrics at the end of each session. The program curriculum was derived from the CDC DSMES Toolkit. The curriculum content was reviewed and approved by the project site's medical director and Health and Education Outreach director. The program curriculum and planned prompts are displayed in Table 1 in Appendix C. The proposed program timeline can be seen in Table 2 in Appendix D

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DSMES curriculum. Participants of the DSMES program were invited to attend a series of five once-weekly sessions. Before the program's first session, the Zoom virtual meeting room moderator contacted eligible participants via phone and reviewed the program curriculum, participation guidelines, and ethical conduct. The moderator provided technical instructions for using the Zoom virtual meetings platform and Qualtrics online survey platform. Additionally, the moderator requested that participants submit the online informed consent form and the pre-

intervention DKQ Survey. The first session covered the simplified pathophysiology of diabetes, treatment options, and diabetes monitoring. The second session covered common diabetes medications and coping with diabetes. The third session covered healthy eating and strategies for practicing a physically active lifestyle. The fourth session covered preventing and treating acute and chronic complications. The fifth and final session covered problem-solving for special circumstances such as natural emergencies. Behavior change strategies were threaded throughout the program. With this design, the DSMES team addressed the recommended topics in the “2022 National Standards for Diabetes Self-Management Education and Support” by Davis et al. (2022).

The DSMES program progressed through the curriculum using a weekly virtual group learning environment hosted on the Zoom platform. Each participant received a reminder text 24 to 48 hours before the upcoming session to attend. The text also reminded participants to email their weekly blood glucose readings log to the project lead. The same one-hour class session was offered each Thursday at 12:00 p.m. and each Friday at 4:00 p.m. to accommodate varying participant availabilities.

In anticipation of the need for classes provided in both the English and Spanish languages, this DNP project followed the existing format of the organization’s Healthy Mind, Body, and Soul classes, which were held in English and Spanish simultaneously. An English-speaking educator and a Spanish translator simultaneously dictated the course content. The participants selected the language of audio output they preferred to listen to. The course facilitators encouraged interaction for collaborative problem-solving among the participants to promote peer learning, as supported by Vygotsky’s Collaborative Learning Theory. See Appendix C for an overview of the DSMES program curriculum and discussion prompts.

Data Collection. This DNP project incorporated several data sources and indicators to observe how the telehealth DSMES program affected glycemic control, diabetes health literacy, and participant satisfaction with the telehealth classroom platform. The HgbA1C, results of DKQ, self-generated blood glucose readings, number of hypoglycemic events, and results from a satisfaction survey were collected as the data observed.

The participants’ sociodemographic data (age, gender, health insurance coverage, and preferred language) were collected to describe the sample’s characteristics and determine the applicability of the project’s findings. Appendix E summarizes the variables/outcomes that were measured and how they were used to analyze the data collected.

Data for glycemic control. The HgbA1C measures the average blood glucose level over three months before laboratory testing (CDC, 2022c). The project lead obtained the most recent HgbA1C values for each participant through the electronic health record (EHR) before initiating the DSMES class sessions and planned to reassess the levels again at weeks six, 12, and 24. No extra costs were associated with HgbA1C measurements outside of costs incurred from standard primary care visits. These values were extracted from the EHR system. In addition, participants were asked to keep a log of self-generated blood glucose readings collected from a home glucometer device. Tracking the trend of self-generated blood glucose readings assisted with identification of excursions in glycemic control that could affect the HgbA1C, including hypoglycemic events, defined as blood glucose level of less than 70 mg/dL (ADA, 2022b). It also helped to identify opportunities to review self-management behaviors and problem-solving for improved glycemic control. Participants were asked to email or text their logs as an electronic log or a picture of a hand-written log to the project lead. These files were destroyed after they

were transferred into the password-protected data collection sheet to maintain participant privacy.

Data for health literacy. The project lead obtained permission to use the English and Spanish DKQ by Garcia et al. (2001). The DKQ can be seen in Table 4 in Appendix F. The DKQ was administered before the first DSMES sessions and planned to be reassessed at weeks six and 24. The DKQ is a validated multiple-choice questionnaire that can be delivered in English and Spanish. Garcia et al. (2001) developed a bilingual Spanish and English version of the DKQ and tested its reliability and validity in Starr County, Texas. It contains 24 “yes” or “no” questions about diabetes with an option to check off “I don’t know.” There is no defined cutting point or range by the DKQ authors to define health literacy. The DNP project lead defined 90% of correct answers in the DKQ as a reflection of achieving diabetes health literacy. The Cronbach’s alpha coefficient for the DKQ was 0.78, indicating sufficient reliability. A Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.70 to 0.95 is acceptable (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). The project lead used an aggregate percentage of correct answers at each data collection point. It used the paired t-test statistical analysis to determine if the data reflected improved diabetes health literacy.

Data for participant satisfaction of telehealth DSMES platform. Following the end of each class session, attendees received a cellular phone text message with a link to a Qualtrics online survey in both English and Spanish to evaluate participant satisfaction with the telehealth classroom platform using three questions incorporating responses ranked in a Likert scale. The information received from the participant satisfaction survey was used to evaluate if they found the telehealth DSMES format helpful, easy to use, and if they would recommend other individuals with diabetes to attend the class. The survey tool was not validated or tested for reliability. Still, as a QI project and not a research study, this survey was accepted as a feedback tool to improve the program following PDSA cycles.

Interaction. The design of the telehealth DSMES program incorporated synchronous learning sessions where the class facilitator threaded thought-provoking questions to encourage discussion and collaborative problem solving. This design was based on the Lev Vygotsky CLT (McLeod, 2018; Miller, 2013). Because collaborative learning served as the underlying theory for the class design, interaction was measured by the number of sessions attended.

Evaluation Plan

To evaluate the effects on glycemic control, diabetes health literacy, hypoglycemic episodes, and participant satisfaction, the project lead implemented the *Study* and *Act* portions of the PDSA cycle.

Study

The data were organized in Microsoft Excel Spreadsheets and analyzed through Intellectus Software and QI Macros. The pre- and post-intervention mean HgbA1C and the mean correct percentage of the DKQ survey scores were evaluated using the paired t-test statistical analysis to identify if the data demonstrated a statistically significant change between data collection time points. The alpha threshold was set at $p=.05$. Analyses of the pre- and post-intervention data were used to determine if glycemic control and health literacy changed after application of the DSMES program.

The computer software QI Macros organized the daily data of patient-generated blood glucose levels into control charts. The rules for a X-bar and S Control Chart were used to identify a special cause effect that would reflect if changes in the data were attributed to the DNP project implementation.

Act

The interpretation of the data analysis guided the lead author to make an evidence-based decision on whether to adopt, adapt, or abandon the project changes. Adopting the practice change entails having confidence that the project implementation had made clear improvements in the clinic practice as evidenced by the data analysis.

Results

Descriptive statistics of participant demographics are presented. The HgbA1C was analyzed as the outcome measure using a paired samples *t*-test. A control chart was used to analyze any process changes in the participant-generated daily blood glucose (BG) values. The 24-item DKQ by Garcia et al. (2001), a three-question Participant Satisfaction Survey results, and participant interaction were also evaluated.

Implementation

Due to unexpected challenges with receiving support staff from the project site's administrative leaders to match this project's proposed timeline, the DSMES intervention was delayed from a start in August 2022 to an actual start date of October 14, 2022. To meet the time constraints of the Southern California State University DNP Consortium program, the lead author adjusted to running a five-week cycle rather than two rounds of DSMES cycles. The planned data collection for HgbA1C at 12 weeks and 24 weeks after the commencement of DSMES intervention was changed to a pre-intervention value and a post-intervention value at six weeks after implementation. Likewise, the DKQ could not be administered 24 weeks after DSMES implementation, as the data could not be collected until after the university submission deadline for this project. Instead, DKQ data were collected at the beginning of the DSMES program and after the last session.

Demographics

The project lead identified 85 eligible patients through a query of the electronic health records (EHR). Of the 85 identified, 55 (64.7%) expressed interest in participating in telehealth DSMES classes, 14 (16.47%) declined, 15 (17.65%) did not respond to the phone calls or voicemails, and one (1.18%) was no longer assigned under the care of the project location by the time the classes commenced. The mean HgbA1C for eligible participants ($n = 85$) at the time of recruitment was 11.14% ($SD = 1.46$).

A convenient sample of nine participants signed consent forms and attended at least one of the five classes. Of the nine participants, all were female (100%), three preferred English as the primary language (33.33%), and six preferred Spanish as the primary language (66.67%). Eight participants were of Hispanic/Latino descent (88.89%), and one was of African American descent (11.11%). Six participants were treated with exogenous insulin (66.67%), and three were treated with oral medications only (33.33%). The participants ranged from 35 to 72 years of age, with a mean age of 52.4 ($SD = 10.13$) and a median age of 53.

The telehealth DSMES program consisted of five weekly class sessions of one-hour duration per session. One participant attended all five sessions (11.11%), one attended four sessions (11.11%), two attended three sessions (22.22%), one attended two sessions (11.11%), and four attended only one session (44.44%). Table 5 and Table 6 in Appendix G display the demographics.

Serum Glycated Hemoglobin

The project's outcome measure to determine if telehealth DSMES classes improve glycemic control is the HgbA1C level collected through venous blood draw and processed by a third-party laboratory. Three participants (33.33%) did not complete the post-intervention HgbA1C test, and one participant (11.11%) was no longer a patient of the project site and thus could no longer participate in the project. Therefore, the data were adjusted for paired pre-intervention and post-intervention data to only include data points from participants who completed a pre-intervention HgbA1C and a post-intervention HgbA1C ($n = 5$). Because the sample is very small and would invalidate the two-tailed paired samples *t*-test, the Mann-

Whitney U Test was used to determine if the DSMES intervention influenced a difference in the median HgbA1C. The Intellectus Software calculated the Mann-Whitney U Test analysis, and the result was not significant based on an alpha value of .05, $U = 5.5, z = -1.47, p = .142$. The mean rank for the post-intervention HgbA1C was 4.10 and the mean rank for the pre-intervention HgbA1C was 6.90. This suggests that the post-intervention HgbA1C ($Mdn = 8.70$) was not significantly different from the pre-intervention HgbA1C ($Mdn = 10.30$). Although not statistically significant, there was a reduction from the pre-intervention median HgbA1C of 10.3% to the post-intervention median HgbA1C of 8.7%. The results are presented in Table 7 in Appendix G. A boxplot of the medians is presented in Figure 6 in Appendix G.

Daily Blood Glucose

Self-generated blood glucose (BG) readings were utilized as a process measure to identify any trends in daily BG levels. All participants were asked to submit a log of their daily BG readings throughout the program; the self-generated blood glucose reading logs were submitted weekly. Two participants submitted logs of their self-generated BG readings. To evaluate if any process changes occurred to BG levels as a result of telehealth DSMES classes, the BG values logged in each of the two participants' EHR were extracted and placed in a control chart using QI Macros, which calculated a mean BG level of 290.7 mg/dL within an upper control limit of 531.4 mg/dL and a lower control limit of 50.0 mg/dL. Data points from the BG logs submitted throughout the project were added to the control chart revealing a process change consisting of a new mean BG level of 154.9 mg/dL within an upper control limit of 281.4 mg/dL and a lower control limit of 28.5 mg/dL. One participant had two hypoglycemic BG readings throughout the project. The participant had one fasting BG reading of 67 mg/dL in the second week and one reading of 67 mg/dL in the fifth week. The hypoglycemic events did not require emergency medical interventions. The participant was able to self-correct her BG level with food consumption. The BG control chart can be seen in Figure 7 in Appendix G.

Diabetes Knowledge Questionnaire

The project's lead author measured diabetes health literacy using the DKQ by Garcia et al. (2001). Six participants submitted the pre-intervention DKQ and the aggregate mean of the percentage of correct responses was 74.3%. Only three participants submitted the post-intervention DKQ, where the aggregate mean of the percentage of correct responses was 58%. To maintain participant anonymity, the project lead used the online survey platform Qualtrics to collect DKQ responses. The hyperlink was not linked to identifiers, so comparing pre-intervention and post-intervention DKQ response tied to a patient identifier was not achieved. Thus, a paired samples t-test analysis could not be performed to evaluate if the project influenced any statistically significant differences in the DKQ outcomes. The participants were asked to submit the DKQ before the first telehealth DSMES class session on October 14, 2022. Two submissions were received on October 19 yielding correct scores of 88% and 67%. A submission on October 26 yielded a score of 79%, and a submission on October 27 was 50% correct. Two additional submissions were received on October 28 with scores of 88% and 75%. Rather than the intended pre-intervention DKQ scores, the submissions received reflected the intra-intervention scores. The final day of DSMES class sessions was November 11, 2022. The participants were asked to immediately complete and submit another DKQ through Qualtrics. Three submissions were received after the classes concluded, one each on November 13, 2022, December 16, 2022, and January 6, 2023. As time progressed after the sessions concluded, the percentage of correct responses decreased to 63%, 58%, and 54%, respectively. A bar graph depicts the aggregate DKQ percentage of correct responses (see Figure 8 in Appendix G).

Satisfaction Survey

Participants completed a satisfaction survey of three questions at the end of each class session. Each response was based on a Likert scale, with one point representing the least level of satisfaction and five points representing the highest level of satisfaction. One participant completed the survey after the first week, two participants completed the survey after the second week, two completed the survey after the third week, one completed the survey after the fourth week, and four participants completed the survey after the fifth week, providing 10 responses throughout the program. The first question asked how useful the program was in helping participants manage their diabetes. The mean score for the first question was 4.56 (SD = 0.73). The second question asked how easy teleconferencing was in delivering the educational classes. The mean score for the second question was 4.40 (SD = 1.26). The third question asked how likely the participant was to recommend the telehealth DSMES class to someone with diabetes. The mean score for the third question was 5 (SD = 0). Table 8 in Appendix G displays the outcomes of the Participant Satisfaction Survey.

Interaction

The DSMES class design threaded group discussions and collaborative problem-solving throughout each session. Therefore, interaction was measured by the number of class sessions attended. Two participants who attended most of the five sessions shared that they enjoyed learning from and with their peers. The participant who attended all five sessions did not submit a post-intervention blood specimen to measure the HgbA1C to evaluate an effect from the DSMES classes. The participant who attended four of the five sessions paradoxically had an increase in HgbA1C from 9.2% to 10.1%. The greatest improvement in HgbA1C was from a participant who attended just one session, from 10.4% to 7.1%.

Discussion

This DNP project aimed to implement interactive telehealth DSMES classes to improve glycemic control amongst adults with uncontrolled DMT2 in the outpatient setting. This section discusses the results, how the findings reflect or differ from the literature, and their implications for clinical practice. Limitations to this project, recommendations, and implications to clinical practice are also discussed.

Glycemic Control

Although the project's sample size produced limitations in assessing whether there was a significant change in glycemic control, the data from this intervention group hints toward clinical significance as evidenced by improvements in the HgbA1C and the self-generated daily blood glucose (BG) levels. In evaluating the data from participants who provided a HgbA1C value before and after the DSMES classes, the median HgbA1C improved from 10.3% before the DSMES classes to a median score of 8.7%. The improvement in HgbA1C is further supported by the change noted in the daily BG average control chart, where the mean BG decreased from 290.7 mg/dL pre-intervention to 154.9 mg/dL post-intervention. The project yielded a 1.6% reduction in HgbA1C scores, a greater reduction in HgbA1C than the reported 0.6% to 0.74% expected from DSMES participation (Beck et al., 2017; Chrvala et al., 2016; Davis et al., 2022). The project's finding was affected by the small sample size of five participants in which pre-and post-HgbA1C were obtained. Two of these five participants had higher post-intervention HgbA1C measurements than baseline, whereas the remaining three had decreased HgbA1C measurements. Two of the participants with improvement decreased their HgbA1C by at least 3%.

Nevertheless, the results imply clinical significance because a 1% decrease in HgbA1C can result in 45% less risk of developing chronic complications due to diabetes and an annual medical cost savings of \$335.04 for all-cause costs and \$1,248.13 diabetes-related costs for one person. Nationally, it can decrease annual expenditure on diabetes care by \$42.5 billion (CMS, 2019; Nathan, 2014). Therefore, if participating in this DSMES project helps sustain optimum HgbA1C levels in selected patients, the project's outcomes will promote meaningful health and financial benefits for its participants.

Health Literacy, Participant Satisfaction, and Interaction

Diabetes Knowledge Questionnaire

The results of the DKQ reflected an inverse outcome than what was expected. Rather than an improved score in the DKQ, the aggregate percentage of correct answers decreased from 74.31% to 58%. This outcome does not reflect a true pre- and post-intervention diabetes literacy score because of the confounding factor that initial DKQ submissions were being submitted during the five-week program. Since participants submitted responses once the classes commenced, they received information that would help them choose the correct answers. Participants were asked to complete the initial DKQ survey before the first day of DSMES classes on October 13, 2022. Submissions were not received until October 19, 2022, with additional submissions received through October 28, 2022, totaling six submissions. Therefore, the aggregate score of 74.3% correct DKQ responses is more reflective of the intra-intervention knowledge acquisition. Furthermore, one must consider that the post-intervention DKQ results may have been influenced by the time after the program ended before post-intervention responses were submitted.

The final DSMES class session was held on November 11, 2022. The participants were asked to submit new DKQ responses immediately at the end of the class session. Of the 10 participants who attended at least one DSMES session, only 3 provided a post-intervention DKQ response, submitted on November 13, 2022, December 16, 2022, and January 6, 2023. A study by Baker and Robinson (2018) looked at pre- and post-instruction knowledge retention for adult students in an agricultural class. The students received educational instruction from pedagogies of direct instruction and experiential learning. Baker and Robinson (2018) found that six weeks after instruction, the student's knowledge level from both groups reflected their pre-instruction knowledge level. Baker and Robinson's (2018) literature review suggests that greater knowledge retention is obtained when deeper learning is increased over time, as opposed to a short course of instruction. This mirrors the recommendation that DSMES is most effective when contact time is greater than 10 hours and over more than 2.5 months (Beck et al., 2017; Chrvala et al., 2016; Davis et al., 2022; Lynch et al., 2019).

The lead author designed contact and duration of this project's DSMES program to five hours over five weeks to limit attrition over time. It is possible that a longer duration for DSMES contact could improve knowledge retention amongst participants, but this may present challenges, as it was difficult to maintain participation throughout this project. Additionally, the lack of participant submission of post-intervention DKQ surveys could be mitigated if a portion of the class session was dedicated to completing the surveys. The participants were given the independence to submit the surveys after logging offline from the class. The participants' reading levels were not assessed and could have influenced the response rate. Designated time during the final telehealth class session for participants to complete the surveys may have produced an increased response for data collection.

Participant Satisfaction

The Participant Satisfaction Survey produced the desired results, reflecting satisfaction with the content and the class delivery mode. The lead author anticipated that early responses to the survey may have been lower, particularly with Question 2, “How easy was the use of teleconferencing for delivering this educational class?” due to a possible lack of familiarity with the online classroom modality. Although two participants found the online classroom somewhat difficult, the remaining eight responses reported it as easy. A promising response throughout the five weeks of class sessions is that respondents consistently reported they are very likely to recommend the DSMES class to someone with diabetes, reflecting they found value in attending the class session. This mirrors the findings by Orlando et al. (2019), where patients and their caregivers reported satisfaction with telehealth services as it facilitates access to care from a convenient geographical location.

Interaction

Interaction in the telehealth DSMES program played a key element in the design of the class sessions. Within Lev Vygotsky’s Collaborative Learning Theory, socialization, and collective problem-solving, with the guidance of an instructor, assist learners in forming new concepts and internalizing learned information (McLeod, 2018; Miller, 2013). Vygotsky called this scaffolding within the Zone of Proximal Development. The small sample size of this DNP project offered a greater opportunity for the participants to converse about their experiences and questions about managing DMT2. Threaded throughout each class session were thought-provoking questions such as “What is the hardest part about eating healthy for you,” “What do you usually do to add movement in your daily routine,” and “What are your thoughts about taking insulin?” The discussions that arose were unique to each class session. The participants engaged with each other, sharing experiences such as personalized strategies to manage diabetes and the challenges of coping with lifestyle and social changes when living with diabetes. Although engagement and satisfaction levels with the class format were high, the data did not reveal improved glycemic control amongst the two participants who attended the greatest number of sessions. Thus, interactivity within this sample did not associate with improved glycemic control.

Limitations

Participation

This DNP project focused on patients empaneled at one of the 12 clinical sites. Eighty-five eligible participants were identified and contacted, though only nine (10.6%) attended at least one DSMES class session. Although limited participation led to restrictions in collecting sufficient data to draw statistically significant conclusions from this project, the amount of participation yielded a slightly greater response than the estimated less than 7% of individuals with diabetes who utilize DSMES services, as reported by Chrvala et al. (2016). When factoring in how many participants attended all five DSMES sessions, only 1.2% of eligible participants fully committed to attending the entire program. Fourteen (16.4%) of the eligible participants declined to attend. The most common reason for decline (35.7%) was conflicting schedules between DSMES class sessions and their occupational schedule. These participants expressed the ability to attend if classes were held after standard business hours or on the weekends.

Data Collection and Analysis

Three factors that influenced the limitations on data analysis were challenges with support from the project site, flaws in the data collection design, and participant nonadherence to submitting the requested data.

Project site support. The project site's CMO and CEO fully supported implementing this DNP project. Challenges occurred with receiving support from department leaders. The Health Education and Outreach (HEO) department leaders expressed challenges with providing staff to assist the lead author with the DSMES program endeavor. The lead author requested assigned personnel for the DSMES team by June 2022. The HEO department leader sought IRB approval before allocating resources for this DNP project. The lead author received IRB approval in August 2022. In late September 2022, the HEO department assigned one staff member to fill the room moderator and technical support position and connected the lead author with a certified Spanish translator. As a result, DSMES team training, participant recruitment, and informed consent could not commence until the beginning of October 2022. Subsequently, the DSMES program was implemented from October 14, 2022, to November 11, 2022. In response to meeting university deadlines, the intervention implementation and data collection timeframe was reduced. The implemented project timeline adjusted for the unforeseen challenges with obtaining a DSMES team is displayed in Table 9 in Appendix D.

Design flaw. The lead author incorporated the online survey software Qualtrics to collect responses to the DKQ and the Satisfaction Survey. In an attempt to maintain participant anonymity, responses to the DKQ and the Satisfaction Survey were not linked to participant identifiers. While this protected participant identities, the lead author could not link pre-intervention and post-intervention responses to individual participants to analyze the individualized effects of the DSMES program, most particularly to the DKQ scores. The assumption that the aggregate scores from pre-intervention and post-intervention can be evaluated against each other failed to produce substantial evidence because not all participants submitted responses. The responses received could not be matched to evaluate if the submissions came from the same participants or different ones; therefore, analyses of any outcome changes are unreliable. In addition, the DKQ submissions were not received in the requested pre-intervention time frame and the immediate post-intervention time frame. Therefore, the perceived decrease in DKQ scores could be attributed to the possibility of the responses from different participants without a matched pre- and post-score. Response submissions could have also influenced the DKQ scores during the actual intervention and months after the conclusion of the interventions. These confounding factors limit the evaluation of a true pre- and post-intervention response.

Nonadherence to participant responsibilities. As previously mentioned, submitting data from the project's designed timeline skewed the validity of the intervention responses. Health literacy outcomes via the DKQ could not be analyzed as a direct effect of the DSMES classes on previous diabetes knowledge. Furthermore, only two of the nine participants submitted logs of their daily blood glucose values, with one participant providing submissions for five weeks and the other submitting values from only one week. As such, the lead author could only analyze blood glucose changes before the intervention against values after the intervention amongst these two individuals. While the process improvement, as can be seen in the control chart in Figure 7 in Appendix G, yielded the expected results, analysis of the aggregate values for the entire cohort would produce data that can be more generalizable.

Despite these limitations, the pre- and post-intervention HgbA1C values analysis offered information to evaluate if the DNP project's aim to improve glycemic control for adults with

uncontrolled diabetes type 2 via the implementation of interactive telehealth DSMES was achieved. Five of the nine participants (55.6%) completed the post-intervention HgbA1C lab draw, which was analyzed against the pre-intervention HgbA1C value extracted from the EHR. There was an aggregate improvement in HgbA1C of 1.3% without serious adverse effects, a greater reduction than the reported 0.6% to 0.74% improvement in HgbA1C reported by Beck et al. (2017), Chrvala et al. (2016), and Davis et al. (2022). Although statistical significance was not achieved, the aggregated decrease in HgbA1C reflects that telehealth DSMES classes may improve glycemic control in adults with uncontrolled DMT2.

Clinical Implications

As a pilot program at the project site, future cycle improvement opportunities exist. Despite the challenges faced in implementing this DNP project, DSMES classes' effect on glycemic control suggested outcomes similar to the literature. The improvements in glycemic control suggest clinical implications to enhance DSMES delivery processes and data collection design. Although this project did not receive the expected participation during the project design, it suggests that additional cycles with adjustments will also contribute to the body of knowledge for achieving diabetic glycemic control with minimal adverse effects.

Recommendations

The improvements in the aggregated HgbA1C and the daily BG values suggest clinical value to interactive telehealth DSMES classes. The data collected were insufficient due to the limited number of participants and design flaws in the collection process. Despite the challenges faced during the pilot of DSMES classes, the lead author recommends additional cycles of DSMES classes while adjusting for the changes needed to improve the data collection process. In the language of the PDSA cycles, the lead author recommends adapting the change process.

Encouragement for involvement from all the providers and staff at the clinical site to refer eligible participants for telehealth DSMES classes may increase the potential for a larger sample size. In addition, class times should accommodate the participants' availabilities. Because the most common response for non-participation with telehealth DSMES classes was conflicting schedules with occupational responsibilities within standard business hours (37.5%), offering classes outside of standard business hours may yield more participant attendance. Furthermore, attaching coded participant identifiers to the Qualtrics survey responses to the DKQ and Participant Satisfaction Survey will allow investigators to run a paired t-test statistical analysis to accurately evaluate any significant effects of the DSMES classes. Although technical support was available throughout the project, designated time to assist the participants with completing the online surveys may have yielded more submissions. While language translation in this sample did not interfere with interactivity and delivery of the class content, future sessions with larger samples may benefit from separating the different languages into different group sessions to mitigate difficulties in attending a bilingual class session.

Additionally, this project hypothesized that interaction would influence glycemic control and used the number of classes attended to measure interaction. The lead author recommends future cycles incorporate a tool to measure the amount of interaction for a closer evaluation of its effect on glycemic control. Before initiating another cycle with enriched efforts, debriefing with the participants would provide feedback on other challenges that might help improve their involvement.

Conclusions

The findings from this DNP project reflect that DSMES classes offer improvement in glycemic control for adults with uncontrolled DMT2. Similar to the literature, less than 7% of individuals who would benefit from DSMES classes utilized the resource (Chrvala et al., 2016). Thus, the challenges requiring greater attention include obtaining more support from the clinical site to recruit participants and adapt the class schedule to the needs of the patient population. To address these challenges effectively, one must consider the costs for after-hours personnel to administer DSMES sessions after standard business hours. Nonetheless, as educators and healthcare leaders, nurses must invigorate the healthcare system and its consumers to see the value in developing diabetes health literacy using DSMES programs. As was experienced in designing, implementing, and analyzing this DNP project, it takes great effort and collaboration by different healthcare stakeholders to carry out such an endeavor as offering DSMES classes. The effort may be worthwhile because, as the literature demonstrates, a 1% improvement in HgbA1C can yield a 45% decreased risk of developing chronic complications due to diabetes and a 13% decrease in diabetes-related costs (ADA, 2020; Lage & Boye, 2020; Nathan, 2014). Therefore, the availability of such programs can help people living with DMT2 prevent secondary health complications, decrease healthcare expenditure, and promote an overall better quality of life.

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Appendix A
Figures for Theoretical Frameworks

Figure 1

Lev Vygotsky's Collaborative Learning Theory

Note. This figure was derived from an image shared by Porcello (2017) and adjusted to display additional details of Lev Vygotsky's Collaborative Learning Theory.

Figure 2

Lev Vygotsky's Collaborative Learning Theory Adapted for Telehealth DSMES classes

Note. Figure 2 depicts Lev Vygotsky's Collaborative Learning Theory with the elements of this DNP project. DSMES = diabetes self-management education and support

Figure 3*The Model for Improvement and PDSA Cycle*

Note. A display of the Model Improvement, including the elements of the aim question and the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle. From Institute for Healthcare Improvement. (2022).

Improving health and health care worldwide: IHI. Retrieved March 4, 2022, from

<http://www.ihl.org/>

Figure 4*The PDSA Cycle with Cycle Components*

The PDSA Cycle for Learning and Improving

Note. A diagram of the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle with the components of each segment of the cycle. From Institute for Healthcare Improvement. (2022). *Improving health and health care worldwide: IHI*. Retrieved March 4, 2022, from <http://www.ihl.org/>

Figure 5

The PDSA Cycle with Cycle Components Adapted for Telehealth DSMES Classes.

The PDSA Cycle for Learning and Improving

Note. The Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle displayed with the elements of this DNP Project. From Institute for Healthcare Improvement. (2022). *Improving health and health care worldwide: IHI*. Retrieved March 4, 2022, from <http://www.ihl.org/>. DSMES = diabetes self-management education and support

Appendix B

Participant Satisfaction Survey

Participant Evaluation Form: Diabetes Self-Management and Education Support (DSMES)

Thank you for attending this class! We look forward to receiving your insight to improve upon this program.

PROGRAM EVALUATION: (please complete the following questions to evaluate the DSMES program)

1. How useful was this program in helping you to manage your diabetes?

1. ¿Qué tan útil fue esta clase para ayudarlo a controlar su diabetes?

Not at all useful / Not very useful / Somewhat useful / Useful / Very useful

Nada útil / No muy útil / Algo útil / Útil / Muy útil

2. How easy was the use of teleconferencing for delivering this educational class?

2. ¿Qué tan fácil fue el uso de teleconferencias para impartir esta clase educativa?

Very difficult / Somewhat difficult / Neither easy nor difficult / Somewhat easy / Very easy

Muy difícil / Algo difícil / Ni fácil ni difícil / Algo fácil / Muy fácil

3. How likely are you to recommend this class to someone else with diabetes?

3. ¿Qué tan probable es que recomiende esta clase a otra persona con diabetes?

Very unlikely / Somewhat unlikely / Neither likely nor unlikely / Somewhat likely / Very Likely

Muy improbable / Algo poco probable / Ni probable ni improbable / Algo probable / Muy probable

Appendix C

Table 1: Diabetes Self-Management Education and Support Curriculum Overview 2022

Table 1

Diabetes Self-Management Education and Support Curriculum Overview 2022

Dates	October 13 (12 pm – 1 pm) October 14 (4 pm – 5 pm)	October 20 (12 pm – 1 pm) October 21 (4 pm – 5 pm)	October 27 (12 pm – 1 pm) October 28 (4 pm – 5 pm)	November 3 (12 pm – 1 pm) November 4 (4 pm – 5 pm)	November 10 (12 pm – 1 pm) November 11 (4 pm – 5 pm)
	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5
Planned Content	Review of curriculum, participation guidelines, ethical conduct, instructional use for Zoom and Qualtrics, pre-intervention DKQ.	Pathophysiology and treatment options Monitoring	Healthy coping Medication Use	Healthy Eating Physical Activity	Acute complications Chronic complications
Planned Prompts	What do you already know about diabetes? What would you like to get out of these sessions? Initial administration of DKQ.	What is diabetes? What are risk factors for diabetes? What can you do to manage your diabetes? Why is self-monitoring your blood glucose important? When should you check your blood glucose? What desirable ranges for your blood glucose?	How does stress affect blood glucose? What activities can you do to manage your stress and diabetes? How does oral medication help bring your blood glucose down? How does insulin bring your blood glucose down? When is the best time to take your medication?	What are nutrition recommendations for people with diabetes? What are carbohydrates, and how do they affect blood sugar levels? How will you adjust your current nutritional intake to achieve better glycemic control? How does physical activity affect blood sugar?	What is hypoglycemia? What is hyperglycemia? How do you manage these events? What is diabetic ketoacidosis? How do sick days affect your blood sugar? What can you do to prepare for severe weather or crisis preparedness in regard to managing your diabetes?

Dates	October 13 (12 pm – 1 pm) October 14 (4 pm – 5 pm)	October 20 (12 pm – 1 pm) October 21 (4 pm – 5 pm)	October 27 (12 pm – 1 pm) October 28 (4 pm – 5 pm)	November 3 (12 pm – 1 pm) November 4 (4 pm – 5 pm)	November 10 (12 pm – 1 pm) November 11 (4 pm – 5 pm)
	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5
		What do you do if your blood glucose is too low or too high?	What can you do to make sure you take your medication as prescribed? What do you do if you have questions about your medications?	How will you incorporate physical activity into your daily routine? How can you incorporate friends and family into your plans for physical activity?	What immunizations are recommended for people with diabetes? How does diabetes affect your eyes? How often should you have your eyes examined? Why are diabetic foot exams important? How often should have your feet checked? How does diabetes affect dental/oral health? How often should you have a dental exam? How does diabetes affect your kidneys?

Notes. Each class module was presented two different days in the same week to accommodate for participant schedule availability. Participants attended only one session per week.

Appendix D Timeline

Table 2
Proposed Timeline

Timeline: Month	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	April
IRB approvals											
Establish education material to train staff.											
Recruit participants											
Train DSMES team.											
Implement telehealth DSMES program.											
Data collection and analysis.											
Finalize project document and poster											
Project dissemination											

Table 9
Implemented Timeline

Appendix E

Table 3: Summary of Planned Variables, Measurements, Assessments & Analyses

Table 3

Summary of Planned Variables, Measurements, Assessments & Analyses

Variable Name (Definition)	Pre-implementation (Baseline) (e.g., at initiation of implementation of improvement/change)	During implementation (e.g., Week 6)	Post Implementation- (e.g., Week 12)	Follow Up (e.g., Week 24)	Source	How it will be measured? Level of measurement	Why used in project	How it will be analyzed/used in analysis?
Hemoglobin A1C (HgbA1C)	X	X	X	X	EHR	Continuous	Outcome measure	Paired t-test analysis between weeks 0 and 6, then between weeks 0 and 12, and again between weeks 0 and 24. Identify changes to glycemic control and evaluate if the outcomes are sustained.
Diabetes Knowledge Questionnaire	X		X	X	Pre and post-knowledge questionnaires prepared by the author	Ratio of correct answers to total questions	Process measure	Paired t-test analysis between weeks 0 and 6 and then between weeks 6 and 24. Evaluate if participants' health literacy improved

Variable Name (Definition)	Pre-implementation (Baseline) (e.g., at initiation of implementation of improvement/change)	During implementation (e.g., Week 6)	Post Implementation- (e.g., Week 12)	Follow Up (e.g., Week 24)	Source	How it will be measured? Level of measurement	Why used in project	How it will be analyzed/used in analysis?
Self-generated blood glucose readings		X			Participants log their BG daily and share with project leader on a weekly basis.	Continuous, aggregate weekly mean	Process measure	X-bar and S-control chart Identify glycemic excursions. Participants and DSMES course instructor will collaborate on problem-solving for improved glycemic control What test will you use
Participant satisfaction survey			X		Participants	Likert scale and categorical	Outcome measure	Evaluate the program strengths and challenges to improve future program implementation
Hypoglycemic events		X			Participants	Count	Balancing measure	Control chart: C-chart
Patient's preferred language (English or Spanish)	X		X	X	EHR	Count	Description of sample	Frequency, percentage

Variable Name (Definition)	Pre-implementation (Baseline) (e.g., at initiation of implementation of improvement/change)	During implementation (e.g., Week 6)	Post Implementation- (e.g., Week 12)	Follow Up (e.g., Week 24)	Source	How it will be measured? Level of measurement	Why used in project	How it will be analyzed/used in analysis?
Insurance coverage (Medi-Cal, Medicare, private insurance, no insurance)	X		X	X	EHR	Categorical	Description of sample	Frequency, percentage
Annual income	X		X	X	Patients	Continuous	Description of sample	MMM, SD, range
Patient age Recorded in years	X		X	X	EHR	Continuous	Description of sample	MMM, SD, range
Patient gender 1=Male 2=Female 3=Other 4=Prefer not to disclose	X		X	X	EHR	Categorical	Description of sample	Frequency, percentage

Notes. EHR = electronic health record, MMM = mean, median, mode, SD = standard deviation

Appendix F
Diabetes Knowledge Questionnaire

Table 4
Diabetes Knowledge Questionnaire

Item #	Preguntas Questions	Sí Yes	No No	No sé I don't know
1.	El comer mucha azúcar y otras comidas dulces es una cause de la diabetes.		√	
1.	Eating too much sugar and other sweet foods is a cause of diabetes.		√	
2.	La cause común de la diabetes es la falta de insulina efectiva en el cuerpo.	√		
2.	The usual cause of diabetes is lack of effective insulin in the body.	√		
3.	La diabetes es causada porque los riñones no pueden mantener el azúcar fuera de la orina.		√	
3.	Diabetes is caused by failure of the kidneys to keep sugar out of the urine.		√	
4.	Los riñones producir la insulina.		√	
4.	Kidneys produce insulin.		√	
5.	En la diabetes que no se está tratando, la cantidad de azúcar en la sangre usualmente sube.	√		
5.	In untreated diabetes, the amount of sugar in the blood usually increases.	√		
6.	Si yo soy diabético, mis hijos tendran más riesgo de ser diébeticos.	√		
6.	If I am diabetic, my children have a higher chance of being diabetic.	√		
7.	Se puede curar la diabetes.		√	
7.	Diabetes can be cured.		√	
8.	Un nivel de azucar de 210 en prueba de sangre hecha en ayunas es muy alto.	√		
8.	A fasting blood sugar level of 210 is too high.	√		

9.	La mejor manera de checar mi diabetes es haciendo pruebas de orina.		√	
9.	The best way to check my diabetes is by testing my urine.		√	
10.	El ejercicio regular aumentará la necesidad de insulina u otro medicamento para la diabetes.		√	
10.	Regular exercise will increase the need for insulin or other diabetic medication.		√	
11.	Hay dos tipos principales de diabetes: Tipo 1 (dependiente de insulina) y Tipo 2 (no-dependiente de insulina).	√		
11.	There are two main types of diabetes: Type 1 (insulin-dependent) and Type 2 (non-insulin-dependent).	√		
12.	Una reacción de insulina es causada por mucha comida.		√	
12.	An insulin reaction is caused by too much food.		√	
13.	La medicina es más importante que la dieta y el ejercicio para controlar mi diabetes.		√	
13.	Medication is more important than diet and exercise to control my diabetes.		√	
14.	La diabetes frecuentemente cause mala circulación.	√		
14.	Diabetes often causes poor circulation.	√		
15.	Cortaduras y rasguños cicatrizan mas despacio en diabéticos.	√		
15.	Cuts and abrasions on diabetics heal more slowly.	√		
16.	Los diabéticos deberían poner cuidado extra al cortarse las uñas de los dedos de los pies.	√		
16.	Diabetics should take extra care when cutting their toenails.	√		
17.	Una persona con diabetes debería limpiar una cortadura primero yodo y alcohol.		√	
17.	A person with diabetes should cleanse a cut with iodine and alcohol.		√	

18.	La manera en que preparo mi comida es igual de importante que las comidas que como.	√		
18.	The way I prepare my food is as important as the foods I eat.	√		
19.	La diabetes puede dañar mis riñones.	√		
19.	Diabetes can damage my kidneys.	√		
20.	La diabetes puede causar que no sienta en mis manos, dedos y pies.	√		
20.	Diabetes can cause loss of feeling in my hands, fingers, and feet.	√		
21.	El temblar y sudar son señales de azúcar alta en la sangre.		√	
21.	Shaking and sweating are signs of high blood sugar.		√	
22.	El orinar seguido y la sed son señales de azúcar baja en la sangre.		√	
22.	Frequent urination and thirst are signs of low blood sugar.		√	
23.	Los calcetines y las medias elásticas apretadas no son malos para los diabéticos.		√	
23.	Tight elastic hose or socks are not bad for diabetics.		√	
24.	Una dicta diabética consiste principalmente de comidas especiales.		√	
24.	A diabetic diet consists mostly of special foods.		√	

Notes. Includes the DKQ-24 and correct responses. √ = correct answer. From “The Starr County diabetes education study,” by A. A. Garcia, E. T. Villagomez, S. A. Brown, K. Kouzekanani, and C. L. Hanis, 2001, *Diabetes Care*, 24(1), pp. 20-21
<https://doi.org/10.2337/diacare.24.1.16>

**Appendix G
Results**

Table 5
Demographics

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Insulin		
Yes	6	66.67
No	3	33.33
Language		
English	3	33.33
Spanish	6	66.67
Marital Status		
Single	4	44.44
Unknown	1	11.11
Married	3	33.33
Widowed	1	11.11
Insured		
Yes	7	77.78
No	2	22.22
Gender		
Female	9	100
Ethnicity		
African American	1	11.11
Hispanic/Latino	8	88.89

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Table 6
Demographics of Age and Sessions Attended

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>	Min	Max	<i>Mdn</i>
Age	52.44	10.13	9	35	72	53
Sessions attended	2.33	1.5	9	1	5	2

Table 7

Two-Tailed Mann-Whitney Test for Glycated Hemoglobin (HgbA1C) by Pre- or Post-DSMES Classes

Variable	Post-DSMES		Pre-DSMES		<i>U</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
	Mean Rank	<i>n</i>	Mean Rank	<i>n</i>			
HgbA1C	4.1	5	6.9	5	5.5	-1.47	.142

Note. DSMES = Diabetes Self-Management and Support

Figure 6

Boxplot of Glycated Hemoglobin (HgbA1C) by Pre- or Post-DSMES Classes

Note. DSMES = Diabetes Self-Management and Support

Figure 7
Control Chart of Daily Blood Glucose Values

Note. CL = center line, LCL = lower control limit, UCL = upper control limit

Figure 8
Diabetes Knowledge Questionnaire Outcomes

Table 8
Summary Statistics Table for Participant Satisfaction Survey

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>	Min	Max	<i>Mdn</i>
Question_1	4.56	.73	9	3	5	5
Question_2	4.4	1.26	10	2	5	5
Question_3	5	0	10	5	5	5

Note. Each question was based on a Likert Scale with one point for least level of satisfaction and five for the highest level of satisfaction.